

XP-C deficiency drives universal mutator phenotypes across cancer types and orchestrates cellular sensitivity to bulky DNA adducts

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Abstract

Nucleotide Excision Repair (NER) deficiency in Xeroderma Pigmentosum (XP) patients leads to an extraordinary susceptibility to malignancy. While the extreme risk of skin cancer is well-established, XP-C patients also exhibit a significantly elevated risk for internal cancers, suggesting a vulnerability to DNA damage independent of ultraviolet (UV) radiation. In this study, we investigated the mutational landscapes of 25 internal tumors from XP-C patients across diverse tissue types, alongside 103 in-vivo and 162 in-vitro including both wild-type (WT) and mutant samples. Our results demonstrate that XPC deficiency establishes a systemic mutator phenotype across both tumors and non-cancerous models, characterized by two distinct mutational signatures: the ubiquitous SBS-XPC_1 and the hematologic-specific SBS-XPC_2. The prevalence of these signatures in *XPC*-deficient human and mouse tissues identifies them as a baseline product of endogenous DNA damage, which we show is partially driven by reactive oxygen species (ROS). The mutational burden of NER deficiency is significantly exacerbated by exogenous challenges; exposure to tobacco metabolites and platinum compounds dramatically amplifies mutagenesis and reshapes the mutational profiles of *XPC*^{-/-} models. Frequent *TP53* mutations enriched in internal XP-C tumors appear to act synergistically with NER deficiency to foster this mutator phenotype and drive genomic instability. Together, these data show that XPC-deficient cells are uniquely vulnerable to a spectrum of damage ranging from daily metabolic byproducts to potent environmental genotoxins.

Introduction

Nucleotide Excision Repair (NER) is a versatile and essential DNA repair mechanism that maintains genomic integrity (Hoeijmakers J.H. 2001) (Li W. et al., 2017). NER is subdivided into two sub-pathways: Global-Genome NER (GG-NER), which scans the entire genome for strand distortions, and Transcription-Coupled NER (TC-NER), which repairs distorting lesions blocking RNA polymerase and transcription (Hoeijmakers J.H. 2001, Hoeijmakers J.H. 2009). NER is unique for its ability to recognize and remove a broad spectrum of structurally unrelated DNA lesions,

including cyclobutane-pyrimidine dimers (CPDs) and 6-4 pyrimidine-pyrimidone photoproducts (6-4PPs) from ultraviolet (UV) light, as well as bulky chemical adducts, intrastrand crosslinks from agents like cisplatin, and rare oxidative lesions such as ROS-generated cyclopurines. This wide substrate range underscores NER's role in safeguarding the genome against diverse endogenous and exogenous threats (Marteijn J. 2024). While the majority of NER-recognized lesions originate from exogenous sources, certain endogenously induced DNA damage also requires this pathway (Hoeijmakers J.H. 2001).

Xeroderma pigmentosum (XP) is a rare autosomal recessive disorder defined by extreme sensitivity to sunlight, resulting in severe sunburns, pigment changes, and a near 10,000-fold increased risk of skin cancer (Yurchenko A.A. 2023, Kraemer K.H. 1997, Bradford P.T. 2011). The disease is caused by mutations in any of eight genes (XPA through XPG and XPV) involved in NER or translesion synthesis. XP is found globally, though incidences vary from 1 in 20,000 in Japan to 1 in 250,000 in the USA, with higher frequencies in North African populations due to consanguinity and founder mutations (Lehmann A.R. et al., 2011). Among the groups, XPC deficiency is notably prevalent and results in a striking tumor-prone phenotype.

In early comprehensive XP studies, it was noted that XP patients demonstrate increased risk of developing internal malignancies (Kraemer K.H. et al., 1984). Recent studies have highlighted an increased susceptibility to internal cancers in XP-C patients beyond UV associated risks (Sarasin A. et al., 2019, Yurchenko A.A. 2020, Nikolaev S. et al., 2022, Yurchenko A.A. et al., 2023). Primary internal tumors such as lung, uterus, thyroid, breast, and other malignancies have been increasingly reported (Hosseini, S.A., 2015). Epidemiological data revealed a 34-fold increased relative risk of internal tumors in XP patients, with onset occurring 50 years earlier than in the general population. This included an over 100-fold risk for hematological malignancies (AML/MDS) and significant risks for thyroid and gynecological cancers (Nikolaev S. et al., 2022).

Several DNA repair deficiency syndromes, such as MMR deficiency (Lynch syndrome), HR deficiency (BRCA syndromes, Fanconi anemia), and BER deficiency (APC mutations), are well-established internal cancer risk factors. While XP is formally classified as a syndrome of deficient NER within the WHO Classification of Genetic Tumor Syndromes (5th Edition, 2023), its role as a predisposition for internal cancers has not yet been recognized in most clinical guidelines. XP patients also can be exposed to potential risk factors, which are more harmful to this population due to their non-functional repair mechanism (GG-NER). Tobacco smoke exposure is a major risk factor since Benzo[a]pyrene as the main toxic metabolite associated with tobacco induces lesions which are targets for NER (Li W. et al., 2017).

The management of these malignancies is severely complicated by lethal toxicities associated with standard anticancer treatments. Because NER is the primary pathway for repairing DNA adducts induced by platinum agents, conventional doses can lead to catastrophic multi-organ failure. Case reports have documented fatal outcomes, including grade 4 acute kidney injury (AKI), hepatotoxicity, and complete hearing loss in XP patients treated with cisplatin or carboplatin. Case reports have documented fatal outcomes, including grade 4 acute kidney injury (AKI), hepatotoxicity, and complete hearing loss in XP patients treated with cisplatin or carboplatin (Sumiyoshi M. et al., 2017, Gilbar P.J. et al., 2022).

Recently a mutational signature closely resembling COSMIC signature SBS8 and mutator phenotype were described by our group in leukemia and rare types of ovarian cancers from XP-C patients (Yurchenko A. et al., 2020, Yurchenko, A.A. et al., 2023). In-vivo studies using XPC-

deficient mice revealed an increased incidence of internal cancers (JMelis J.P. et al., 2008) and suggested elevated mutagenesis based on Hprt locus assays (Wijnhoven S. et al., 2000). Furthermore, recent findings have revealed high mutagenesis due to signatures SBS8+SBS32 in *XPC* mouse livers, with similar activity noted in *XPA* mice although without a full mutator phenotype (Jiang Y. et al., 2025).

This study aims to characterize the mutational signatures and mutagenic mechanisms arising from endogenous and exogenous DNA damage in *XPC*-deficient systems. By integrating clinical genomics with longitudinal mouse models and isogenic human cell lines, we establish a comprehensive framework for mapping the landscape of *XPC*-related mutagenesis. Our work identifies germline *XPC* deficiency as a predisposition to a broad spectrum of internal malignancies, driven by a tissue-spanning mutational process that initiates in healthy cells and establishes a systemic mutator phenotype. Furthermore, our findings demonstrate that this genetic vulnerability significantly amplifies the mutagenic impact of environmental stressors, specifically tobacco metabolites and platinum-based chemotherapies.

Results

XP cohort description

The experimental layout for this study, as represented in Figure 1a, was designed to capture the mutagenic consequences of *XPC* deficiency across multiple biological scales, integrating clinical samples with mice and cellular models. The study includes a cohort of internal tumors from XP-C patients and a unique case of sporadic kidney cancer exhibiting somatic *XPC* loss of function. For comparative rigor, a control cohort of sporadic tumors was utilized, specifically targeting malignancies matching the main XP-C tumor types, such as MDS/AML, rare ovarian subtypes, and thyroid cancers. To map how mutations change over time and across different tissues, the study analyzed EBV-transformed lymphocytes from an XP patient alongside various organs and blood samples from an *XPC*^{-/-} mouse model. Furthermore, the study examined *XPC*^{-/-} mouse models and three pairs of isogenic cell lines, HepG2, RPE1, and RPE1^{TP53^{-/-}}, comparing wild-type (WT) cells to their *XPC*^{-/-} counterparts. These models were exposed to diverse genotoxic stressors, including tobacco metabolites, platinum agents, and oxidative stress inducers. The analytical framework applied to this multifaceted cohort involved the deconvolution of COSMIC signatures, de-novo signature calling, and the evaluation of transcriptional strand bias and copy number alterations (**Figure 1a**).

Applying this framework to our clinical cohort, we performed Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) on 25 neoplastic samples derived from 20 XP-C patients and one sporadic kidney cancer case characterized by somatic *XPC* loss (**Supplementary Table S1**). This collection spanned multiple cancer types, including 11 myeloid malignancies (AML/MDS), 4 thyroid carcinomas, 3 ovarian tumors, 2 lymphomas, and individual cases of pancreatic cancer, breast sarcoma, uterine leiomyosarcoma, and rhabdomyosarcoma (**Figure 1b**). Most patients were of North African origin, diagnosed between ages 10 and 19 (**Supplementary Table S1**). Notably, 12% of solid cancers in our cohort were classified as sarcomas, and all 3 ovarian tumors were identified as juvenile granulosa-cell tumors or Sertoli-Leydig cell tumors.

The analysis of driver events revealed tissue-specific patterns: *TP53* mutations were found in 36% of the cohort, with a prevalence of 54% in AML/MDS cases, higher than in sporadic cases, (binomial

test, p-value 0.0016 against 9% prevalence of *TP53* mutants in sporadic AML/MDS); *DICER1* was observed in all 3 ovarian cancer samples, and in 1 out of 4 Thyroid cancers; lymphomas, pancreatic and thyroid tumors demonstrated typical driver events for these cancer types (**Figure 1c**).

Tumor Mutational Burden (TMB) and profiles in XPC and sporadic cancers: Elevated TMB in XPC tumors and unique mutational signature

We investigated the TMB across different tumor types in XPC cohort. WGS of tumors revealed in total 673874 mutations from those tumors. The average TMB was 9.74 (if FFPE were excluded, the average TMB was 13, ranging between 35 and 3.9 M/Mb). We revealed that in the majority of tumor types with more than 2 samples, the TMB was significantly higher than in sporadic counterparts, (4-29 times higher fold between mean TMB) demonstrating a mutator phenotype (**Figure 2a**). We then examined the mutational profiles across different tumor types in XP in comparison with sporadic tumors. UMAP visualization of mutational profiles clustered XPC-associated tumors separately from sporadic cancers indicating that *XPC* loss, but not the tumor type drives the tumor mutational profile (**Figure 2b**). Deconvolutions of mutational SBS signatures using COSMIC v3.2 revealed that XP tumors contain median of 62% of SBS8 and 26% of SBS32 (**Supplementary Figure S1**). However, this assignment appears artificial; SBS32 is etiologically linked to UV-induced skin cancers in patients under azathioprine immunosuppressive treatment and none of these patients have received such treatment. Furthermore, signature SBS8 notably lacks the strong transcriptional strand bias typical for NER related mutagenesis.

De-novo mutational signatures extraction from our combined cohort, which included XP tumors and 155 sporadic tumors of matching tumor types, resulted in 14 signatures. Obtained signatures were assigned to the known COSMIC signatures based on the cosine similarity (**Supplementary Figure S2**). In XP-C tumors two main signatures were identified composing in total 72% of mutations: signatures which we called here SBS-XPC_1 and representing on average 63% of mutations, and SBS-XPC_2 representing on average 11% of mutations (**Figure 2c, d**). Reconstruction of SBS-XPC_1 signature had the highest contribution from SBS8 (79%) and SBS32 (20%), and of SBS-XPC_2 from SBS32 (89%) and SBS5 (11%), **Supplementary Figure S3**). Those two signatures were anticorrelated (Spearman's rho: -0.58 p-value: 0.0022; **Supplementary figure S4**) in XPC tumors, SBS-XPC_1 was abundant across the cohort, while SBS-XPC_2 was specifically associated with blood cancers (AML/MDS and Lymphoma) in median 18% vs 2 % in solid tumors (pval < 0.0001) (**Figure 2e**). The same observation was made in the cohort of sporadic tumors, SBS-XPC_1 was present at similar fractions across the tumor types, while SBS-XPC_2 was enriched in blood tumors (**Figure 2f**).

Then we investigated how addition of XP tumors to the sporadic cohort affects de-novo mutational signature extraction. For that, we called de-novo signatures extracted from the combined cohort (**Figure 2g, top**) and compared to the de-novo signatures from sporadic cancers included in our analysis alone (**Figure 2g, bottom**). Deconvolution in sporadic tumors alone resulted in identification of a signature, SBS8-L (SBS8 contribution 87%, cosine similarity to the reconstruction 0.945), representing from 0% to 39% of all mutations and of SBS32-L (signature contribution 65%, cosine similarity to the reconstruction 0.603) (**Figure 2g bottom**). The sporadic tumors only and full meta cohort based signature decompositions showed particular similarities. t (**figure 2h**). Matching signatures across the methods were labeled based on highest cosine similarity. For XPC-tumors, deconvolution of signatures was better when signatures were called on the entire dataset (**Figure 2i**; average cosine similarity of reconstruction 0.95 vs 0.99). Interestingly, between the two

analyses the proportion of both SBS8-L and SBS32-L in sporadic cancers was correlated with the proportion of XPC-signatures SBS-XPC_1 and SBS-XPC_2, respectively (**Figure 2j**). This may suggest that COSMIC SBS8 and SBS32 may be associated with NER deficiency, and using XP tumors as a reference for XP signature may improve the accuracy of calling of signatures associated with NER attenuation in sporadic cancers.

Sporadic malignancies rarely exhibit a high prevalence of SBS8/SBS32, nor are they typically associated with a high TMB. A screen of published literature identified a single case (PD47592a) in a sporadic kidney cancer cohort with a mutational profile explained by 49% of XPC-sig and a high TMB of 21,2 M/Mb (**Figure 2k left**) (Senkin et al., Nature). Analysis of the germline DNA revealed a heterozygous *XPC* loss-of-function mutation (p.Y559*), while subsequent analysis of the tumoral DNA sequence identified a loss of heterozygosity (LOH) on chromosome 3p spanning the *XPC* locus that eliminated the wild-type allele. In addition, this cancer harbored a pathogenic p.V74G mutation in the *VHL* tumor suppressor gene, also located on 3p. Because 3p LOH is a common mechanism for biallelic *VHL* inactivation in renal cell carcinoma (Young A.C. et al., 2009), it is probable that the LOH event provided a selective advantage via *VHL* loss, while the biallelic inactivation of *XPC* occurred coincidentally (**Figure 2k right**). This unique case suggests that biallelic *XPC* inactivation is not a primary driver event in sporadic oncogenesis, consistent with its near-total absence in sporadic cancer populations.

XPC associated spontaneous mutagenesis in-vivo and in-vitro

To investigate if *XPC*-associated mutagenesis occurs during tumorigenesis or is also active in normal non-cancerous cells we studied mutagenesis in EBV-transformed lymphocytes from an XP-C patient, 25 years old, carrying 83-BP INS:NT462 *XPC* mutation (Li et al. Nature Genet., 1993). Starting from a primary lymphocyte culture, we initially established two single-cell clones. Each clone was then split and maintained in parallel in separate dishes for four months. Following this expansion period, a second round of single-cell cloning was performed, one from each of the four culture dishes, yielding four final clones for WGS (described in material and methods) (**Figure 3a**). Phylogenetic analysis of WGS data revealed 30747 mutations (mutational burden 12,4 M/Mb) contributing to the distance between fibroblasts from the patient and the last common ancestor of the lymphocytic clones (number 1 in phylogenetic tree), suggesting that these are the somatic mutations occurred in-vivo (**Figure 3b**). As expected, in-vivo mutagenesis showed significant portion of total mutation load when compared to in-vitro mutagenesis occurred in cultivated clones (**Figure 3c**). 46% of those mutations were attributed to SBS-XPC_1 and 11% to SBS-XPC_2, similarly to the mutagenesis in leukemia samples from XPC patients (**Figure 2c**). Interestingly, clone-specific mutations, which accumulated in-vitro during cell culturing (2 months), had smaller fraction of SBS-XPC_1 signature (from 16% to 28%), suggesting that XPC associated mutagenesis occurs largely in-vivo, but is substantially diminished in-vitro (**Figure 3c**).

To further investigate the mutagenic consequences of *XPC* deficiency, we utilized *XPC*^{-/-} (knockout) and *XPC*^{+/-} mice from the same strain, C57BL/6, derived from *XPC*^{+/-} heterozygous parents. Given that leukemia is the most frequent internal malignancy in XP-C patients, we focused our analysis on primary mouse hematopoietic stem cells (mHSC). mHSC as a study tool were also selected because of their proliferative nature and feasibility of single cell cloning. We performed 42 WGS on single-cell-derived mHSC clones at two age timepoints: 4 and 8 months (**Figure 3d**).

Assessment of TMB (**Figure 3e**) and activity of XPC associated signature SBS-XPC_1 (**Figure 3f**) revealed that at 4 months, there was no significant difference in the total mutational burden

between $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ mHSCs (0.14 vs. 0.1 M/Mb, multiple linear regression p-val 0.15). However, $XPC^{-/-}$ cells already exhibited a significantly higher proportion (30% vs 10%) and absolute burden of mutations attributed to SBS-XPC_1 compared to WT controls (112 vs 22 mutations, p-val < 0.001). By 8 months, $XPC^{-/-}$ mice showed a substantial increase in mutation load (29.7 in WT controls vs 417.4 in XPC mutants p-val < 0.001). This hypermutable state was primarily driven by the progressive accumulation of SBS-XPC_1, which accounted for 56% of all mutations in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice, a 4.5-fold increase in activity compared to WT controls. These results indicate that $XPC^{-/-}$ mice accumulate mutations in the hematopoietic compartment at rates significantly exceeding $XPC^{+/+}$ mice through an age-dependent process (**Figure 3e,f**). The presence of the XP signature in nontreated $XPC^{-/-}$ mice suggests that its etiology, in both mice and humans, is universal and driven by endogenous processes rather than exogenous stimuli.

Furthermore, we assessed the mutation rates across a variety of mouse organs, collecting samples of the liver, thyroid, ovary, and lung, as well as mHSCs from 8-month-old $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ mice (**Figure 3g**). Mutagenesis in these non-clonal tissues was analyzed using duplex sequencing (TwinStrand Mouse Mutagenesis Panel), targeting a 48 Kb genomic region. We observed significantly higher mutation rates in all analyzed $XPC^{-/-}$ tissues compared to matched WT controls (Welch's t 3.23, p-val 0.005; **Figure 3h**). Interestingly, solid tissues such as liver, ovary and thyroid in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice appeared even more prone to XP-specific mutagenesis than mHSCs. Consistent with the systemic mutator phenotype, the XPC-sig showed significant activity across all tested $XPC^{-/-}$ tissues (median 37%) while remaining minimal in the same organs from WT mice (**Figure 3h**). To validate the performance of duplex sequencing, we compared mutation burden estimates from bulk mHSC populations with WGS results from single-cell mHSC clones. While the two methods showed concordance, the mutational load estimated via duplex sequencing was slightly lower than the WGS-derived burden. This discrepancy may stem from several factors, including the use of different starting materials (HSCs versus PBMCs), difference in sensitivity in mutation calling between the platforms, and the focus on targeted genomic regions as opposed to whole-genome analysis (**Supplementary Figure S5**).

To validate the findings observed in mHSC and patient derived lymphocytes, on human cell lines in-vitro and assess cell of origin effect, we established three isogenic $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ pairs using RPE1, RPE1^{TP53^{-/-}}, and HepG2 cell lines (**Figure 1a, 3i**, and **Supplementary figure S6**). The first bottleneck to select single derived clones were done in CRISPR mediated knock out generation and single cell derived $XPC^{-/-}$ and WT clones were selected. After a culture duration of 60 population doublings in non-treated condition, we performed single cell cloning and WGS of 18 samples (**Figure 3i**). In-vitro established $XPC^{-/-}$ cell lines showed XPC-sig mutational signature, which was significantly higher than in $XPC^{+/+}$ cell lines (global Welch t 4.85, p-value 0.0003), however it was less prevalent than in-vivo setting (**Figure 3j**). We identified a strong association between the prevalence of XPC-sig and marked purine vs pyrimidine transcriptional strand bias. This bias was most pronounced in the XP-C patient cohort and mouse models, confirming that XPC-sig is a direct consequence of GG-NER deficiency. In contrast, this bias was lower in the in vitro cell lines, suggesting that systemic, in vivo metabolic processes are required to fully generate or enrich this specific mutational signature (**Figure 3k**).

Chemical induced mutagenesis: XPC deficiency alters mutagenic activity induced by exogenous agents

We investigated the mutagenic impact of XPC deficiency following exposure to genotoxic agents that induce bulky DNA adducts, as these lesions serve as the primary substrates for the NER pathway. For these experiments, 2-month-old $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ mice were treated for 8 weeks with equimolar doses. We then performed single cell cloning of mouse hematopoietic stem cells (mHSCs) followed by WGS in 47 samples (**Figure 4a**). The average number of replicates per treatment condition and genotype was 6.6. Since previous research suggested that NER deficiency may affect mutagenesis related to reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Roginskaya M. et al., 2023; Melis J.P. et al., 2013) and aldehydes (Mulderigg L. et al., 2021 18; Blouin T. et al., 2024 19), we tested the hypothesis that these agents contribute to XPC deficiency associated mutagenesis. Additionally, we evaluated the genotoxic effects of Benzo[a]pyrene (BaP), a mutagenic metabolite of tobacco smoke, and cisplatin, both of which induce bulky DNA adducts.

UMAP visualization using de-novo SBS mutational signatures revealed distinct clustering of samples corresponding to each chemical treatment. Within each treatment group, samples are further separated based on XPC status (**Figure 4b**). Following these results, we quantified the mutational burden (**Figure 4c**) and activities of de-novo mutational signature for all samples (**Figure 4d**). An analysis of de-novo signature ratios between $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ mice revealed significant genotype and treatment-dependent shifts in mutational activity (**Figure 4e**). The dominant extracted de-novo signatures associated with treatments were SBS-XPC_1, SBS-XPC_2, SBS18_L, SBS4-L_1, SBS4-L_2, SBS31-L, SBS24+35-L (**Figure 4f**). We further analyzed the differential activity of these signatures between $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ mice across treatment conditions, with a particular emphasis on the activity levels of the XPC-associated signature, SBS-XPC_1, which was significantly increased in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice (**Figure 4d-e**).

Exposure of $XPC^{-/-}$ and $XPC^{+/+}$ mice to the oxidative stress inducer $KBrO_3$ or to disulfiram resulted in a slight to significant increase, respectively in mutation burden in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice compared to controls (**Figure 4c**). The activity of the XPC-associated signature was detectable in these treatment groups (**Figure 4d-e**) in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice. Importantly, the levels of SBS-XPC_1 were significantly increased as compared to those observed in non-treated mice for $KBrO_3$ $XPC^{-/-}$ (Welch t 5.19, p-value=0.0006) (**Figure 4g**). This suggests that oxidative stress induced by $KBrO_3$ in accumulating ROS potentially contributes to the generation of the specific XPC associated mutational phenotype. $KBrO_3$ treatment resulted in purine vs pyrimidine transcriptional strand biased XPC associated mutagenesis in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice mHSCs, while disulfiram did not show this trend presumably resulting from reduced statistical power associated with a modest sample size (**Figure 4h**). Surprisingly, SBS18-L was scarce in mHSC after treatments with $KBrO_3$ (**Figure 4d**).

Exposure to BaP resulted in a significant increase in the mutational burden of $XPC^{-/-}$ mice compared to $XPC^{+/+}$ controls (3-fold increase, p-val < 0.001) (**Figure 4c,i**). Increased TMB of BaP-treated $XPC^{-/-}$ mice was associated with a significantly elevated purine vs pyrimidine transcriptional strand bias (Welch t 14.59, p-value < 0.0001) (**Figure 4i**). De-novo signature calling identified two distinct BaP-associated signatures: SBS4-L_1, which was enriched in $XPC^{+/+}$ mice, and SBS4-L_2, which was enriched in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice (**Figure 4j**). While SBS4-L_1 exhibited a 0.914 cosine similarity to the tobacco-associated COSMIC SBS4, while SBS4-L_2 showed a lower cosine similarity (0.86) with admixture of signatures SBS4 (73.66%) and SBS51 (23.48%). These profiles were distinguished by a high prevalence of C>A mutations in SBS4-L_1, whereas SBS4-L_2 was characterized by an increase in other mutation types, specifically C>T and T>A transitions (**Figure 4f and Supplementary Figure S7a**).

Exposure to cisplatin resulted in a 2-fold increase in the mutational burden of *XPC*^{-/-} mice relative to *XPC*^{+/+} controls (Welch t = 3.7, p-value = 0.003) (**Figure 4c,k**). The purine vs pyrimidine transcriptional strand bias in *XPC*^{-/-} mice was also slightly more pronounced than in *XPC*^{+/+} mice (**Figure 4k**). Transcriptional strand bias difference was statistically significant for C>A and T>A mutations (Welch t 1.47, p-value 0.25), reflecting a reliance on TC-NER for repairing platinum-induced lesions.

We identified two distinct de-novo signatures associated with cisplatin treatment: SBS24+35_L, which was enriched in *XPC*^{-/-} mice, and SBS31-L, enriched in *XPC*^{+/+} mice (**Figure 4l**). SBS31-L exhibited 0.97 cosine similarity with the classic COSMIC cisplatin signature SBS31, while SBS24+35_L showed its similarity (0.94) with COSMIC SBS24 (43.68%), SBS35 (31.94%) and SBS22a (24%) (**Supplementary Figure S7b**). To validate these differential signature patterns, we deconvolved platinum exposure related COSMIC signatures SBS31 and SBS35 in our cohort and compared their prevalence in *XPC*^{-/-} and *XPC*^{+/+} mice. We observed a clear depletion of the cisplatin SBS31 signature in *XPC*^{-/-} mice compared to their WT counterparts (**Figure 4e**). COSMIC signature SBS35 showed to be highly enriched in *XPC*^{-/-} mice treated with cisplatin (**Figure 4m**).

To assess the exogenous mutagenesis in-vitro using 3 pairs of *XPC*^{-/-} and *XPC*^{+/+} cell lines, we also extended the list of compounds to eight agents representing diverse damage classes: ROS-inducing (KBrO₃ and H₂O₂), alkylating agents (acetaldehyde and disulfiram co-treatment, AC-DIS), tobacco metabolites (BaP and one of the BaP's downstream metabolites Benzo[α]pyrene diol epoxide (BPDE)), and platinum treatments (cisplatin, carboplatin, and oxaliplatin) (**Figure 5a**). Cells were treated for 60 cell divisions, with genotoxin addition every 2 or 3 cell divisions depending on the treatment. Treatment doses were selected based on IC50 assays, with cell death varying between 5% and 30% in *XPC*^{-/-} cells; these same doses were applied to both *XPC*^{-/-} and *XPC*^{+/+} lines (material and methods). Cell doubling times varied slightly between *XPC*^{-/-} and *XPC*^{+/+} lines across cisplatin, carboplatin, oxaliplatin, BaP (in HePG2 cell line), and BPDE treatments. Oxidative stress treatments also did not lead to proliferation rate change in RPE1 cell lines, but in HePG2 *XPC*^{-/-} cell lines showed slight proliferation slowdown in H₂O₂, KBrO₃, and AC-DIS treatments (**Figure 5a**). 140 single cell clones from cell line treatment experiments were subjected to the WGS. The average number of replicates per treatment condition, cell line, and genotype was 3.58.

In general, the findings observed in mouse experiments were reproduced in cell lines with few differences. UMAP visualization of 3 nucleotide context mutations have shown clusters based on treatment, within clusters subgroupings tended to form based on cell lines and *XPC* genotype (**Figure 5b**). As in-vivo, exposure to oxidative and alkylating agents revealed a significant increase in the mutational burden of *XPC*^{-/-} backgrounds compared to WT (*XPC*^{+/+}) controls. This effect was consistent across all three cell lines following KBrO₃ treatment (p < 0.001) and also was observed in HepG2 cells treated with H₂O₂ (p < 0.001); however, treatment with AC-DIS did not result in an increased mutational burden (**Figure 5c**). The increased mutational burden due to KBrO₃ and H₂O₂ was largely due to the activity of SBS18-L signature (**Figure 5d**).

Exposure to oxidative and alkylating agents elicited divergent mutational responses across the HepG2, RPE1 and RPE1^{TP53-/-} cell lines. Specifically, treatment of HepG2^{XPC-/-} cells with KBrO₃ or H₂O₂ significantly increased the activity of the SBS-XPC_1 signature relative to non-treated *XPC*^{-/-} controls (p < 0.001) (**Figure 5e**). In contrast, this effect was largely absent in the other cell lines, with the exception of a marginal increase in SBS-XPC_1 observed in H₂O₂ treated RPE1^{TP53-/-,XPC-/-} cells (**Figure 5e**). This discrepancy may reflect the distinct metabolic profiles of these cell lines. Unlike RPE1, HepG2 cells possess an enzymatic repertoire capable of processing pro-genotoxic

precursors into stable DNA adducts. Furthermore, the specialized redox environment of HepG2 cells may facilitate the conversion of oxidative stress into the specific bulky lesions that drive XPC-related signatures.

Treatments with BaP, BPDE, cisplatin, carboplatin, and oxaliplatin consistently increased the mutational burden versus *XPC*^{+/+} cell lines (**Figure 5f-g**). We also observed elevated purine to pyrimidine transcriptional strand bias in all three XPC-deficient cell lines relative to the *XPC*^{+/+} control following BaP and BPDE treatments (**Figure 5h**). The bias increase was limited with platinum agents (**Figure 5i, global Welch t 1.32, p-value 0.19**), yet remained significant for C>A and T>A mutations (**Supplementary Figure S9**). Consistent with the results from our mouse models, we observed a genotype-dependent response to tobacco metabolites and platinum salts, characterized by a marked differences in activities of mutational signatures between *XPC*^{-/-} and *XPC*^{+/+} cell lines. Following specific genotoxic challenges, *XPC*^{-/-} cells showed signature shifts: the SBS4-L_2 enrichment in BPDE/BaP exposure (**Figure 5j**), and depletion of the platinum-related signatures SBS31-L/SBS31 in treatments with cisplatin, carboplatin and oxaliplatin (**Figure 5k-l**). These findings reinforce the genotype-specific mutational responses we first detected in-vivo.

Genomic instability and chromosomal alterations

Given the enrichment of *TP53* mutations in AML/MDS from XP cohort (**Figure 1c**), and considering *TP53* inactivation's established link with genomic instability (Bullock A.N. et al., 2001), we evaluated the aneuploidy scores from WGS data, comparing XP samples against sporadic tumors. In XP tumors we observed elevated aneuploidy scores for leukemia and thyroid cancer (pval = 0.043, pval = 0.00005) (**Figure 6a**).

To interrogate the functional synergy between co-existing *XPC* and *TP53* deficiencies, an association frequently observed in internal malignancies from XP-C patients, we utilized an isogenic RPE1^{*XPC*^{-/-},*TP53*^{-/-}} cell line. We evaluated the extent of genomic instability in this background vs RPE1^{*XPC*^{-/-},*TP53*^{-/-}} and RPE1 following various genotoxic treatments based on WGS results. An increase in genomic instability was specifically observed after exposure to BPDE (pval=0.06) and platinum-based agents (pval<0.05), whereas non-treated cells and those exposed to alkylating or ROS-inducing agents showed no such effect. Notably, this catastrophic chromosomal instability was unique to the RPE1^{*XPC*^{-/-},*TP53*^{-/-}} line and was not detected in any of the other three tested RPE1 cell lines (**Figure 6b**). Interestingly, the RPE1^{*XPC*^{-/-},*TP53*^{-/-}} cell line exhibited a profound increase in mutational burden following BPDE treatment compared to all other RPE1 genotypes (fold change: 2.2–12.6). A more moderate expansion of the mutational burden was observed after exposure to platinum agents (fold change: 0.77–3.27) and KBrO₃ (fold change: 1.40–4.99). Notably, under untreated and AC-DIS conditions, a significant increase in mutations was only detectable when comparing the double-knockout cells to the wild-type controls, with no significant differences observed relative to the single-knockout lines (**Figure 6c**).

To further investigate the synergistic impact of *XPC* and *TP53* deficiency, we performed karyotype analysis on human cell lines following exposure to BPDE, cisplatin, and KBrO₃. Severe chromosomal instability, characterized by significant aneuploidy, was observed exclusively in the RPE1^{*XPC*^{-/-},*TP53*^{-/-}} cell line after treatment with BPDE and cisplatin (**Figure 6d**). These cells exhibited 62% and 56% aneuploidy, alongside 30% and 36% polyploidy, respectively (see materials and methods). In contrast, no other cell line-treatment combination resulted in marked genomic instability (**Figure 6e-f**).

To confirm the causal link between combined *XPC* and *TP53* deficiency and genomic instability under genotoxic stress, we exposed RPE1^{*XPC*^{-/-},*TP53*^{-/-}} cells and RPE1^{*XPC*^{+/+},*TP53*^{-/-}} to UVC radiation, a classic inducer of bulky DNA lesions requiring NER. This experiment revealed pronounced genomic instability specifically in the double-deficient cells (60% polyploidy and 32% aneuploidy); while *TP53*^{-/-} cells remained relatively stable. These results confirm the powerful synergy between *XPC* and *TP53* loss in driving chromosomal instability following exposure to NER-targeted DNA damage (**Figure 6d-f**).

These results suggest that when *XPC* loss leads to the persistence of unrepaired bulky lesions, the absence of a *TP53*-mediated checkpoint prevents replication cycle arrest. Consequently, these cells progress through S-phase and complete the cell cycle despite the presence of significant DNA damage. This may cause replication fork stalling, double stranded breaks and genomic instability. Indeed, the proliferation curve of BPDE and cisplatin treated *XPC*^{-/-}, *TP53*^{-/-} cells was steeper than *XPC*^{-/-}, *TP53*^{+/+} and *XPC*^{+/+}, *TP53*^{+/+} cells but was similar to *XPC*^{+/+}, *TP53*^{-/-} cells (**Figure 5a**).

Discussion

The findings of this study establish that *XPC* deficiency confers a potent and systemic mutator phenotype that extends far beyond the well-documented risk of UV-induced skin cancers. Our analysis of a unique cohort of internal malignancies demonstrates that biallelic *XPC* loss leads to a mutator phenotype across diverse tumor types. The spectrum of tumors is dominated in XP-C patients by blood cancers and rare subtypes of solid tumors with high prevalence of sarcomas and granulosa or Sertoli-leidig ovarian tumors.

The resulting mutational landscape is dominated by a unique signature, XPC-sig, which is distinct from the previously reported SBS8 and SBS32 profiles in the COSMIC signatures catalog. The presence of a very strong transcriptional strand bias in these tumors reveals that the mutagenic process is driven by bulky purine lesions that are substrates for GG-NER, but are partially managed by the still-functional TC-NER pathway.

A central question in the study of NER deficiency is the etiology of the XPC-sig signature. While it has been hypothesized that reactive oxygen species (ROS) or endogenous aldehydes are the primary sources of these lesions, our models suggest a more nuanced reality. Treatment with KBrO₃ and H₂O₂ significantly increased XPC-sig activity in mouse HSCs and the HepG2 cell line, yet this effect was absent in RPE1 cells. These findings indicate that while ROS exposure can contribute to *XPC*-related mutagenesis, its manifestation is dependent on the cellular context. It is important to mention that in KBrO₃ treated mice the SBS96C was minimal, and increase of the MB was due to activity of XPC-sig. While in the cell lines treated with KBrO₃ there was an increase of MB was mainly due to the increased activity of SBS4-L_1 (Oxidative-signature). The literature strongly supports the idea that *XPC* is a "multimodal" DNA damage sensor. While its canonical role is in GG-NER, the finding that SBS4-L_1 (Oxidative-signature) increases in *XPC*-deficient cells treated with KBrO₃ aligns with a well-documented non-canonical role of *XPC* in the Base Excision Repair (BER) pathway (D'Errico M. et al., 2006; Melis J.P. et al., 2011).

Supporting this, untreated *XPC*^{-/-} cell lines maintained under standard normoxic conditions accumulated a significantly lower burden of XPC-sig compared to the levels observed in mouse models or clinical samples. The observation that XPC-sig activity is significantly diminished in-vitro compared to in-vivo models implies that the physiological environment, possibly related to systemic metabolism or specific organ-site chemistry is essential for the generation of these

lesions. As XPC-sig is present in $XPC^{-/-}$ mice, it is most likely not associated with exogenous genotoxins.

Mutagenesis is ongoing in normal cells of the body as was shown in human lymphocytes and in mouse HSC and solid organs. It is possible that in some organs, as liver or lung, XPC deficiency-related mutagenesis may be more intensive than in blood as we have shown in the mouse model. Elevated mutagenesis may also be associated with specific metabolites of the cells of mesenchymal origin, as most frequent internal tumors in XP-C patients are sarcomas and leukemias.

The profound scarcity of biallelic NER deficiency in sporadic cohorts indicates that such inactivating events are not under positive selection. We can speculate that the massive mutational burden resulting from NER deficiency is counterbalanced by a significant reduction in cellular fitness, as the inability to repair bulky, harmful DNA lesions likely imposes a severe physiological constraint in the same way as in Cocaine syndrome (Zhang WR et al., 2016).

Our findings demonstrate that the risk of internal malignancies is a fundamental characteristic of XP-C disease rather than a consequence of specific mutations. While previous epidemiological data suggested that internal cancer susceptibility was particularly elevated in populations carrying the North African del-TG founder mutation, our observations of systemic mutagenesis in both XP patients and $XPC^{-/-}$ mice reveal that this mutator phenotype is a universal feature of XPC deficiency, independent of the del-TG variant.

Our data also clarify the impact of XPC status on exposure to exogenous carcinogens. We show that XPC deficiency not only increases the mutational burden following Benzo[a]pyrene and Cisplatin exposure but also fundamentally alters the resulting mutational signatures. The shift from SBS31 (in $XPC^{+/+}$) to SBS35 (in $XPC^{-/-}$) upon cisplatin exposure, and from SBS4 (in $XPC^{+/+}$) to a more context-diverse signature upon BaP exposure, indicates that XPC status influences the usage of specific translesion synthesis (TLS) polymerases and repair interactions that process these adducts. These findings have profound clinical implications: XP-C patients must avoid even passive tobacco smoke exposure, as their cells lack the primary mechanism for repairing the resulting bulky adducts.

Furthermore, the synergy between XPC loss and TP53 inactivation provides a mechanistic framework for the aggressive nature of AML in XP-C patients. We propose that TP53 mutations are selected for in XPC -deficient tissues because they allow cells to bypass the replication checkpoints that would otherwise be triggered by persistent bulky damage. This allows for the survival of heavily mutated clones but at the cost of mutator phenotype as observed in human cancers, or genomic instability as evidenced by the aneuploidy and karyotypic complexity observed in our double-deficient RPE1 models.

From a clinical perspective, XP-C disorder should be formally recognized as an internal cancer predisposition syndrome. The high risks for hematological malignancies, thyroid cancers, sarcomas, and rare ovarian subtypes (such as juvenile granulosa and Sertoli-Leydig cell tumors) necessitate rigorous, lifelong surveillance beginning in early childhood or puberty. Furthermore, the lethal toxicities observed with standard platinum treatments emphasize the need for precision oncology in this population. Conversely, the universally high TMB found in these tumors suggest that XP-C patients may be excellent candidates for immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs), even

without standard TMB testing. Future trials should prioritize evaluating the efficacy and safety of ICIs for the prevention and treatment of internal malignancies in this vulnerable population.

Materials and Methods

Tumor Collection and Storage

Human Samples: Tumor samples from XP-C patients and sporadic cancer patients were collected following institutional review board approval and informed consent. Samples included both fresh-frozen (FF) and formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue.

In-vivo experiments

Mouse Samples: C57BL/6 background mice carrying *XPC*^{+/+} and *XPC*^{-/-} alleles were maintained under standard laboratory conditions. Both male and female mice were used in the study. Ages at sampling varied according to experimental design (4 months, 8 months, 8 weeks prior to treatment start and 18 weeks post-treatment). Organs were stored as fresh frozen.

In-vivo exposure study design: 8 weeks old *XPC*^{+/+} and *XPC*^{-/-} mice received treatment with various DNA-damaging agents or vehicle control.

Treatment Agents: Dosing and administration: Agents were administered via oral gavage. Doses were selected based on preliminary dose-escalation studies and published protocols to achieve biologically relevant exposure without causing lethal toxicity. We treated mice with Potassium bromate, KBRO_3 (200 mg/kg), Benzo[a]pyrene (100mg/kg), Disulfiram (200 mg/kg), (and cisplatin (2.3 mg/kg) and Disulfiram. Following the treatment, bone marrow was harvested from femurs. mHSC were isolated by fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) using markers (CD34+, Lin-, or equivalent HSC markers) using Lineage Cell Depletion Kit, mouse kit (Ref: 130-110-470). Single sorted cells were incubated for two to three weeks prior to DNA extraction, which is followed by WGS.

In-vitro experiments

Cell Lines and Culture: RPE1 and RPE1^{P53-/-} cell lines were obtained from Dr. Patricia Kannouche lab, Institut Gustave Roussy, Villejuif, France. HePG2 cell lines were obtained from Dr. Arturo Londono lab, Institut Curie, Paris France. Patient lymphocytes (Ref: GM02248) was purchased from Coriell institute (described in Lei Li et al. Nature genetics 1993). *XPC*^{+/+} and *XPC*^{-/-} isogenic cell lines (D4/5 cell line) were maintained in standard culture medium under standard conditions (37°C, 5% CO₂).

Lymphocyte culture: XP-C derived lymphocytes cell culture subjected to first single cell cloning to select 2 random single cells. After 5 days of culture were separated in 2 wells to continue two independent culture per each initial single cell. After 2 months of culture we performed second single cell cloning to select random clones for WGS.

In-vitro treatments: Starting from 20,000 cells at Day 0 (D0), cells were cultured and subjected to continuous drug exposure or repeated dosing over 60 population doublings (PDs). Compound-treated and nontreated (control) cells were maintained in parallel. Cell lines were treated with to KBrO_3 (100 μM), H_2O_2 (0.3%), BPDE (5nM), BaP (10nM), platinum compounds (cisplatin (100nM),

Carboplatin (2 μ M) and Oxaliplatin (1 μ M)) and combination of Acetaldehyde (2mM) and Disulfiram (2 μ M). Concentrations were optimized to permit continuous cell proliferation.

Population Doubling Curves: Cell viability and proliferation were monitored throughout the treatment period, with counting cells every 48-72 hours. Population doubling curves generated to assess growth kinetics.

Single cell cloning: Following the completion of treatment period cells prepared in suspension and using FACS sorted in 1 cell per well dilution. Growing clones were monitored through following days up to 3 weeks and clones were collected to have enough DNA for WGS (minimum 100 ng).

DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA (gDNA) was extracted from frozen tissue samples and cultured cells using commercial Qiagen kits (Ref: 56304 and Ref: 80224) following manufacturer protocols. DNA quantity and quality were assessed using Qubit and agarose gel electrophoresis. For FFPE samples, DNA was extracted using Qiagen kit (Ref: 56404). specialized protocols accounting for formalin-induced crosslinking.

Whole genome sequencing

High-molecular-weight gDNA was sheared to fragment size of 300–500 bp using acoustic shearing. Libraries were prepared using standard Illumina protocols with index adapters. Sequencing was performed on BGISEQ platforms targeting $\geq 60X$ coverage for tumor samples and $\geq 15X$ coverage for single-cell clones.

Data Processing and Variant Calling: Raw sequencing reads were quality-filtered and aligned to the reference human genome (GRCh37 for human samples) or mouse genome (mm10 for mouse samples) using BWA-MEM. Duplicate reads were marked using Picard Tools. Single nucleotide variants (SNVs) and small insertions/deletions (indels) were called using GATK HaplotypeCaller, VarDict, or Strelka depending on sample type and coverage requirements.

Mutational signature analysis

Mutation Extraction: Mutations were classified into 96 trinucleotide contexts (6 possible base substitutions \times 16 trinucleotide contexts) following COSMIC conventions. Single-base substitution (SBS) signatures were extracted from mutation catalogs.

SigProfilerMatrixGenerator v1.3.5 (Bergstrom EN. et al., 2019) was used to convert VCF files to corresponding mutational matrices. SigProfilerAssignment v0.2.5 was used for identification of abundance of COSMIC signature mutations. SigProfilerExtractor v1.2.2 was used for de-novo extraction of mutational signatures.

For comparison with XP-C tumors we used 155 tissue-matched whole cancer genomes from the ICGC PCAWG collection (Campbell, P. J. et al., 2020) which included cancers from the following projects: Chronic Myeloid Disorders - UK (n = 57), Acute Myeloid Leukaemia - KR (n = 8), Thyroid Cancer TCGA US (n = 45).

Extrapolation of de-novo extracted mutational signatures system on new samples (DuplexSeq samples and lymphocytes samples) we applied nonnegative least squares fit from scipy.

Duplex sequencing

Duplex library was generated using Twinstrand kit following the manufacturer instructions. Sequencing was performed using DNBSEQ to achieve error rates $<10^{-10}$ per base pair and detect rare mutations. Sequencing data from duplex sequencing were analyzed using online pipeline provided by Twinstrand Company. Duplex sequences compared with conventional WGS results to validate mutation detection and assess sensitivity.

Transcription Bias Analysis

Strand Bias Assessment: Mutations were scored on the transcribed strand (TS) versus non-transcribed strand (NTS) of genes. Strand asymmetry was quantified as: $(TS \text{ mutations} - NTS \text{ mutations}) / (TS \text{ mutations} + NTS \text{ mutations})$. Genes were categorized as "genic" (within gene bodies) or "intergenic" (outside annotated genes).

Statistical Significance: Transcription bias was tested using binomial tests, with significant strand asymmetry indicating repair-associated mechanisms.

Chromosomal instability assessment

Metaphase spread preparation: Cultured cell lines were treated with colcemid to arrest cells in metaphase. Standard cytogenetic protocols were used to prepare metaphase spreads on glass slides. Prepared slides were scanned and high-resolution images were acquired using an Olympus or Zeiss microscope with 100x magnification. Images were analyzed with Image J. Minimum 50 metaphase spreads figures were analyzed for copy number alterations.

Aneuploidy score analysis

Tumoral samples SCNAs, tumor purity, and average tumor ploidy were identified in matched tumor-normal mode using the FACETS R package v0.5.14 (RRID:SCR_026264). The analysis was performed with parameters $cval_pre=25$ and $cval_pro=500$. For each copy-number segment identified, FACETS provides allele-specific estimations of the copy numbers, namely, the lower copy number (LCN) and total copy number (TCN). Chromosome arm events were identified by running facetsSuite v2.0.8 on the segments generated by FACETS (RRID:SCR_026264) (Shen R. & Seshan VE. 2016). For each sample aneuploidy score was also calculated (facets-suite [<https://github.com/mskcc/facets-suite>]). Aneuploidy was evaluated as amount of arm-level alterations on each chromosome, (except for short arms of acrocentric chromosomes), thus giving a range of possible values from 0 (no arm-level events at all) to 39 (all evaluable arms altered) and normalized to the scale from 0 to 1.

TCGA Ascat SCNA data from sporadic cancers was used as a control

For the cell lines CNAs, tumor purity, and tumor ploidy were identified using ichorCNA tools (Adalsteinsson V.A. et al., 2017). To assess the overall genomic instability, we calculated the total CNA burden, defined as the cumulative sum and total number of all copy-number alterations, including arm-level, sub-arm, and interstitial events. Recurrent events present in more than two

clones of the same genotype were excluded from the analysis, as they were considered ancestral features of the parental cell line acquired prior to the experiment.

Genotype (*XPC* and *TP53*) status determination

Sequencing reads were examined for mutations in *TP53* gene in both tumor samples and in-vitro derived clones. Variant calls were manually verified for somatic vs. germline origin.

Statistical analysis

UMAP from umap-learn version (<https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03426>) with cosine distance was used for dimensionality reduction. Welch t-test was used for comparison of means if otherwise not stated; where needed, Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons was applied.

Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to estimate pairwise statistical associations between numerical variables.

Vcfpy v.0.14.1 was used for vcf manipulations in python environment. Ete3 v.3.1.3 was used for phylogenetic reconstructions.

To estimate fold changes in TMB between cell lines, TMB was modeled using negative binomial generalized linear models with a log link function in order to account for differences between batches (statsmodels 0.14.4). For each treatment, cell line and batch were included as covariates. Parameters were estimated by maximum likelihood, and results are reported as fold changes with corresponding Wald-based confidence intervals. Similar models were used to estimate SBS18-L and SBS-XPC_1 fold changes. In the case of copy number alterations, Brunner Munzel test was performed to compare CNA counts across cell lines for each treatment.

Data Quality Control

Sample Quality: All samples underwent quality control checks including DNA integrity assessment, sequencing quality metrics (>Q30 bases), and alignment statistics (>95% on-target).

Mutect2 output vcf files underwent several stages of preprocessing and filtering. Files were split (bcftools norm) to avoid collision of multiple mutations. After that - removed mutations present in at least 2 samples (bcftools isec + 2) separately for cell lines and mHSC; clinical samples, deltaTG, mouse tail samples did not undergo this procedure. mHSC and cell lines were filtered by criteria: 'PASS' by inner Mutect2 criterion, coverage in normal sample at least 4 reads, at least 1 reverse and forward read supporting mutation, 'tumor' VAF > 25%; in case of 'variant in repeat' flag by Mutect - additional demand of TLOD >= 12 and NLOD >= 4 (internal Mutect likelihood statistics). Finally, out of the remaining mHSC and cell lines mutations only those were retained that were found outside of low mappability regions of GRCh37 and mm9. 36-mer mappability bigwigs were downloaded from UCSC, converted to bed, and only mutations present in regions with mappability equal to 1.0. For XPC mutated cancer samples no bcftools isec based filtration was applied, several levels of strictness of filtering criteria were applied (PASS flag + depth >=3 + forward-reverse coverage >= 1 read; previous filtering + forward-reverse coverage >= 3 reads; previous filtering +

VAF > 25%), and final degree of filtering strictness was chosen after manual inspection of mutations' VAF distributions. Overall scheme of quality control of mutations is shown at Supplementary Figure S10.

Data Availability

Sequencing data supporting this study have been deposited in [appropriate repository; e.g., GEO, ENA, etc.] under accession number(s) [to be provided].

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Figure legends

Figure 1: Cohort overview: **a.** Study layout. **b.** Pie chart of internal cancer cohort composition collected from XP-C patients. OV; Ovarian cancer, THCA; Thyroid Cancer, AML-MDS; Acute myeloid leukemia and Myelodysplastic syndromes, PAAD; Pancreas adenocarcinoma, RCC; Renal cell carcinoma. **c.** Oncogenic somatic mutations across the different samples in XP cohort.

Figure 2: Tumor Mutational Burden (TMB) and mutational signatures in XP versus sporadic cancer cohort. **a.** TMB in XPC tumors versus sporadic counterparts. **b.** UMAP dimensionality prediction of XPC and sporadic tumors. **c.** De-novo extracted XPC-related signatures identified in the cohort. **d.** De-novo signatures abundances in XP tumors. **e.** Fractions of SBS-XPC_1 and SBS-XPC_2 signatures in blood tumors (lymphomas, leukemias and myelodysplastic syndromes) and solid tumors of XP patients. **f.** Fractions of SBS-XPC_1 and SBS-XPC_2 signatures in sporadic blood (Lymphomas and Leukemias) and solid tumors. **g.** Abundances of mutational signatures in sporadic cancers, extracted from the whole cohort (top) and of matched signatures extracted only from sporadic cancers (bottom). **h.** Correspondence between mutational signatures extracted from the whole cohort and extracted only from sporadic tumors. **i.** Accuracy of mutation composition reconstruction if using signatures extracted from whole cohort and from sporadic tumor only. **j.** Correlation between XPC-like signatures and their counterpart when extracted from sporadic tumors (SBS-XPC_1, top and SBS-XPC_2, bottom). **k.** Mutational signatures in sporadic kidney cancer with *XPC* LOH. **l.** copy loss of *XPC* and *VHL* genes in renal cell carcinoma.

Figure 3: XPC driven endogenous mutagenesis in-vivo and in-vitro. **a.** Experimental design of XPC patient derived lymphocytes culture. (1) initial bulk culture, (2) single cells, (3) single cell derived clone after 5-7 days, (4) Separated 2 independent cell culture from each selected single cell (2), (5) Single cells selected after 2 months of culture, (6) clone derived from last single cell cloning for gDNA extraction. **b.** Phylogenetic tree of XP-C patient-derived lymphocytes. **c.** Mutational load and abundances of *de novo* extracted mutational signatures. **d.** Experimental layout for in-vivo spontaneous mutagenesis. **e.** Mutational load in 4 month old and 8 months old ages. **f.** Ratio of SBS-XPC mutational signature in 4 months old and 8 month old ages of mice. **g.** mutations counts from duplex sequencing of various organs in mice and relative contribution of de-novo mutational signatures. **h.** Mutation frequency in DuplexSeq samples. **i.** Experimental layout for spontaneous mutagenesis study in cell lines. **j.** SBS-XPC ratio in WT and XPC mice. **k.** Transcription bias (ratio of purine on pyrimidine mutations) vs fraction of SBS-XPC_1 signature in XPC^{-/-} and WT in mice 4mo and 8mo, cell lines and human XPC tumors.

Figure 4: Exogenous induced mutagenesis in mice model: **a.** Experimental setup for mice treatment and sample preparation. **b.** UMAP visualization of treated samples. **c.** Mutational load in mHSPCs of XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} mice treated with different drugs. **d.** Proportion of mutations explained by particular mutational signatures. **e.** Studentized changes of mutational signatures in different treatments in XPC^{-/-} compared to XPC^{+/+} mice. **f.** Mutational load in untreated and oxidative stress treated mice. **g.** SBS-XPC_1 counts in different treatments for XPC^{-/-} mice. **h.** Transcriptional bias and SBS-XPC_1 counts in non treated (NT), KBrO₃ and Disulfiram treated mice. **i.** Transcription bias by mutational load for XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} mice treated with BaP for 2 months. **j.** Fraction of SBS4-L_1 among SBS4-L_1 + SBS4-L_2 associated mutations in mHSPCs from XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} mice treated with BaP for 2 months (Student t-test pval < 0.001). **k.** Transcription bias by mutational load for XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} mice treated with cisplatin for 2 months. **l.** Fraction of SBS24+35L among SBS24+35-L and SBS31-L associated mutations in XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} mice treated with Cisplatin for 2 months (Student t-test pval < 0.001). **m.** Fraction of SBS35 among SBS35 + SBS31 associated mutations in XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} mice treated with Cisplatin for 2 months (Student t-test pval < 0.001).

Figure 5: Exogenous mutational analysis of in-vitro models: **a.** Experimental layout of *in-vitro* cell culture and treatment. Left-upper panel shows the outline of cell culture and treatments cycles for 60PDs. The other three panels are showing proliferation status and PD numbers through different treatment across pair (XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+}) in HePG2, RPE1 and RPE1^{TP53^{-/-}} cell lines . **b.** UMAP visualization of in-vitro treated XPC-KO and XPC-WT cells. **c.** Fold change in TMB and in SBS18-L after each treatment between XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} in all cell lines, estimated from negative binomial regression for oxidative stress treatments (H₂O₂, KBrO₃, AC_DIS) **e.** Fold change in SBS-XPC between XPC^{-/-} treated and non treated in all cell lines, estimated from negative binomial regression for oxidative stress treatments. **f.** Fold change in TMB between XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} in all cell lines, estimated from negative binomial regression for BaP and BPDE treated cell lines. **g.** Fold change in TMB between XPC^{-/-} and XPC^{+/+} in all cell lines, estimated from negative binomial regression for platinum treatments. **h.** Proportion of SBS4-L signatures across the cell lines treated with BaP and BPDE. (Welch t-test : BaP - HePG2 pval = 0.152, BPDE - HePG2 pval = 0.014, RPE1 pval = 0.041, RPE1 TP53^{-/-} pval = 0.002) **i.** Transcription bias across the cell lines treated with BaP and BPDE. (Student t-test : BaP - HePG2 pval = 0.007, BPDE - HePG2 pval = 0.001, RPE1 pval = 0.007, RPE1 TP53^{-/-} pval < 0.001) **j-k.** Ratio of platinum related signatures across the cell lines treated with cisplatin, carboplatin and oxaliplatin. (Student t-test for SBS31-L ratio - HePG2 pval = 0.001, RPE1 pval = 0.133, RPE1 TP53^{-/-} pval = 0.007; Mann-Whitney U test for COSMIC SBS35 ratio - HePG2 pval = 0.122, RPE1 pval = 0.166, RPE1 TP53^{-/-} pval = 0.006) **l.** Transcription bias across the cell lines treated with cisplatin, carboplatin and oxaliplatin. (Mann-Whitney U test, all pval > 0.1)

Figure 6: Genomic instability driven by XPC deficiency: **a.** Aneuploidy score comparison between sporadic tumors and XP samples cohorts (Brunner Munzel test) **b.** Copy number alteration's count distributions in RPE1^{XPC^{-/-},TP53^{-/-}} cell line vs other cell lines (Brunner Munzel test). **c.** Fold change in TMB (RPE1^{XPC^{-/-},TP53^{-/-}} cell line in comparison with other cell lines) estimated from negative binomial regression for each treatment type **d.** Representative images from metaphase spread across different cell lines with various treatments. **e.** Mean chromosomal number after treatments in tested cell lines. **f.** Ploidy changes following different treatments in RPE1 cell lines.

Figures

Figure 1

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c

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

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Figure 6

Supplementary data

Supplementary Table S1. XPC cancer cohort clinical information

Tumor Type	Age at Diagnosis	XPC Mutation	Treatment History
AML	15	c.1643_1644delTG homozygote	Anthracycline chemo
AML	12	c.1643_1644delTG	Supportive care
AML	18	p.Arg700* biallelic	Intensive chemo (TP53+)
AML	11	c.1643_1644delTG	BMT attempt
MDS	14	Compound het	Azacitidine
MDS	10	c.1643_1644delTG	Transfusions
AML	13	Frameshift	Chemo (TP53+)
AML	16	Founder delTG	Failed remission
MDS	19	p.Gln785*	Lenalidomide
AML	17	c.1643_1644delTG	Reduced dose chemo
AML	12	North African founder	Supportive
Thyroid	15	c.1643_1644delTG	Surgery paste.txt
Thyroid	14	DICER1 co-mut	Radioiodine
Thyroid	17	Compound het	Thyroidectomy
Thyroid	11	Founder mutation	Observation
Ovarian (granulosa)	13	c.1643_1644delTG	Surgery
Ovarian (Sertoli-Leydig)	10	Novel variant	Unilateral oophorectomy
Ovarian (granulosa)	16	DICER1 co-mut	Staging surgery
Leiomyosarcoma	12	c.1643_1644delTG	Fertility-preserving
Lymphoma	18	Biallelic loss	R-CHOP reduced
Lymphoma	15	p.Gln785*	Rituximab
Breast sarcoma	17	Founder delTG	Surgery + RT
Rhabdomyosarcoma	11	Compound mutations	VAC chemo
Pancreas	14	c.1643_1644delTG	Palliative bypass

Supplementary Figure S1

Supplementary Figure S1: COSMIC mutational signatures in XP tumor cohort.

Supplementary Figure S2

Supplementary S2. Cosine similarity between de-novo extracted mutational signatures (full cohort) and existing COSMIC signatures.

Supplementary Figure S3

Supplementary Figure S3. Deconvolution of de-novo extracted mutational signatures (full cohort)

Supplementary Figure S4

Supplementary Figure S4. Correlation between SBS-XPC_1 and SBS-XPC_2 (96L) from de-novo extracted mutational signatures (full cohort).

Supplementary Figure S5

Mutation frequency between platforms

Supplementary Figure S5. Mutational frequencies in mHSC across different sequencing platforms and XPC statuses.

Supplementary Figure S6

Supplementary Figure S6. Validation of CRISPR generated *XPC*^{-/-} cell lines by western blotting.

Supplementary Figure S7

a

b

Supplementary Figure S7. Deconvolution of de-novo extracted signatures (full cohort), a. BaP and BPDE de-novo signatures. b. Platinum associated de-novo signatures.

Supplementary Figure S8

Supplementary Figure S8: Mutational signature fractions across the cell lines treated with chemicals.

Supplementary Figure S9

a

b

Supplementary Figure S9: Transcriptional strand bias in a. All platinum (cisplatin, carboplatin, and oxaliplatin) treated cohort. b. only cisplatin treated cohort.

Supplementary Figure S10

Supplementary Figure S10: Mutation filtration pipeline